

SIMULATION OF THE CONE PENETRATION TEST: DISCRETE AND CONTINUUM APPROACHES

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents the modelling of the cone penetration test using two procedures: a discrete approach and a continuum approach. The discrete approach is based on the Discrete Element Method where a granular material is represented by an assembly of separate particles. Cone penetration has been simulated for both uncrushable and crushable sands. For the continuum approach, the Particle Finite Element Method has been adapted in order to overcome the difficulties posed by the occurrence of large displacements as well as by the geometrical, material and contact nonlinearities of the problem. Both single phase and two-phase (coupled hydromechanical) formulations have been developed and applied. Although not exempt from problems, both approaches yield realistic results leading to the possibility of a closer examination and an enhanced understanding of the mechanisms underlying cone penetration.

1 INTRODUCTION

Penetration problems are widespread in geotechnical engineering. Among them, cone penetration is one of the prime means of soil investigation but its interpretation remains largely empirical especially for sands (Mayne 2007, Schnaid 2009); theoretical approaches are more advanced for clays (e.g. Randolph 2004). A more rational interpretation may benefit from appropriate modelling although it must be recognized that significant challenges arise when numerical analyses of penetration problems are undertaken. Those types of problems involve large deformations as well as geometrical and contact nonlinearities. Also, complex constitutive laws are generally required to represent adequately the mechanical behaviour of geotechnical materials.

The paper presents a summary of some recent work carried out by our group concerning the modelling of penetration problems and, more specifically, the simulation of cone penetration tests. Two approaches have been pursued: discrete modelling and continuum modelling. Granular soils have been modelled by an assembly of distinct particles using the Discrete Element Modelling (DEM). This approach is not practicable in the case of fine-grained materials where a continuum analysis has been favoured. The Particle Finite Element Method (PFEM) has been employed as the preferred numerical technique for this approach.

2 DISCRETE MODELLING

2.1 GENERAL

The use of the Discrete Element Method (DEM) to model the mechanical behaviour of granular materials certainly has important limitations but also a considerable number of advantages (O'Sullivan, 2011). Among the limitations are the generally over-simplified geometrical representation of the particles (often assumed to be spheres) and the need to scale up their size, especially in boundary value problems such as the cone penetration analyses. In spite of this scaling, the resulting calculations are computationally intensive if a sufficiently representative number of particles are considered.

The main advantage is that large strains, displacements and rotations are readily accommodated in the analyses. Also, it is possible to bypass the need for quite sophisticated constitutive models for sands; instead only the contact law between pairs of individual particles are usually required. It should be noted, however, that there is considerable uncertainty over the precise form of those contact laws and their parameters are generally calibrated comparing the macroscopic response of a DEM model and the results of analogous laboratory tests.

First attempts to use DEM to simulate cone penetration tests (Huang & Ma, 1994; Calvetti & Nova, 2005; Jiang *et al.*, 2006) used 2D elements (i.e. disks). Although undoubtedly useful, they fail however to provide a realistic representation of the kinematics of granular deformation. More representative results are obtained using 3D analyses although, so far, they have been limited to spherical shapes (Butlanska *et al.*, 2010a, 2010b; Arroyo *et al.*, 2011; McDowell *et al.*, 2012; Lin & Wu, 2012; Butlanska *et al.*, 2013).

2.2 CONE PENETRATION MODELLING IN CRUSHABLE SANDS

This modelling work has developed virtual calibration chambers, VCC (Arroyo *et al.*, 2011). Analyses have been performed with the PFC3D code (Itasca, 2010); the rotation of spheres has been inhibited in order to capture the limited rotation observed when non-spherical particles are involved. The necessary limitation of the number of particles employed in the analyses has required the adoption of results' filtering (to smooth the oscillation of cone resistance) and to account for chamber size effects, a requirement also necessary in the interpretation of the results to form physical calibration chambers. Another importance difference with the physical system lies in the fact that the way of forming the specimens is quite different in the virtual and in the physical calibration chambers, leading to differences in initial fabric.

In spite of those difficulties, it has been possible to obtain good quantitative agreement between the results of the DEM analyses and the extensive set of data reported by Jamiolkowski *et al.* (2003). The tests were performed on Ticino a medium-size silica sand with mostly sub-rounded grains. Because of the strength of the basic particle material, it was not necessary to account for grain crushing in the analyses. Figure 1 (Arroyo *et al.*, 2011) shows the comparison for a number of tests covering relative densities from 60% to 90% and confining pressures from 40 to 400 kPa.

Figure 1: Comparison between corrected cone resistance from DEM and corrected cone resistance values from physical tests on Ticino sand.

One of the important advantages of using DEM is the possibility to perform observations not only at the microscale (individual particles and contacts) but also at the mesoscale (continuum stress-strain). The mesoscale is particularly useful as the observations have direct counterparts in continuum analysis (Butlanska *et al.*, 2011, 2014).

As an example, Figure 2 shows the computed distribution of radial stress at different radial distances for a dense granular assembly under two different boundary conditions. The distributions close to the axis of the cone closely resemble the experimental observations obtained by Jardine *et al.* (2013) in a physical chamber. Indeed, as shown in Figure 3, the peak values computed from the DEM analyses follow the same quantitative trend as those obtained in the physical chamber tests.

Figure 2: Distribution of radial stresses at different radial distances, r , normalized by cone radius, R_c . Stresses are normalized by cone resistance, a . Normalized depth 0 corresponds to the cone tip position a) No lateral displacement condition (BC3). b) Constant radial stress condition (BC1).

It appears therefore, that in spite of its limitations, DEM analysis is capable of simulating satisfactorily many of the physical features of cone penetration in granular materials. In addition, it is possible to achieve an enhanced understanding of the underlying mechanisms when examining the results at the microscale and at the mesoscale.

Figure 3: Peak values of normalized radial stress versus normalized radial distance (see caption of Figure 2). DEM results and physical chamber observations from Jardine *et al.* (2013).

2.3 CONE PENETRATION MODELLING IN CRUSHABLE SANDS

Granular materials made up of weaker grains, such as calcareous sands, often exhibit significant particle crushing when subjected to high or even moderate stresses. It has been observed (e.g. Almeida *et al.*, 1991) that the pattern of cone resistance increase with relative density is notably different in calcareous crushable sand compared to non-crushable silica sand. This difference results in difficulties when correlations developed for silica sands are applied to materials with crushable grains (Ahmed *et al.*, 2014; Moss, 2014). In this context, the application of DEM analysis is appealing because it allows isolation of the effects of grain strength and crushability. It will be applied to an extreme case, reported by Wesley (2007), where the cone resistance was insensitive to relative density (Figure 4). The material is a volcanic pumice sand, the grains of which are themselves porous.

To perform those analyses, it is necessary to extend the DEM formulation to account for the possibility of grain crushing. Two different approaches have been proposed: the use of multigrain aggregates (Cheng *et al.*, 2003; Bolton *et al.*, 2008) or a multigenerational approach (Marketos & Bolton, 2009; Ben-Nun & Einav, 2010; Bruchmüller *et al.*, 2011) in which a single element breaks and is replaced by a new generation of smaller grains.

Recently, an efficient formulation has been proposed, using the latter approach, that allows the performance of DEM analyses of boundary value problems in a reasonably economical manner (Ciantia *et al.*, 2014, 2015). The main features of this approach can be summarized as follows: a particle failure criterion inspired by the analytical work of Russell & Muir Wood (2009) and Russell *et al.* (2009), a particle spawning procedure based on Apollonian packing and upscaling rules for particle strength and contact constant stiffness parameters for both linear and Hertzian contact laws. As in many multigenerational approaches, mass is not conserved after particle splitting but the missing mass of broken particles is allocated, during post-processing, to finer fractions according to a fractal distribution. In this way, it is possible to track evolving porosity and grain size distribution (GSD). Figure 5 shows the configuration of the spawned particles after the breakage of a single sphere. It has been shown (Ciantia *et al.*, 2015) that this DEM formulation readily captures the macroscopic behaviour of highly crushable granular materials.

Figure 4: CPT results observed in cone penetration tests on pumice sand performed in a calibration chamber. (Wesley 2007).

Figure 5: Apollonian configuration of the spawned particles after the breakage of a single sphere.

The DEM model has been calibrated against oedometer and triaxial tests on the pumice sand used in the calibration chamber tests (Wesley, 2007). For instance Figure 6 shows the comparison with two oedometer tests performed at different densities. Grain size distributions were determined at various values of vertical stress. Figure 7 shows that the grain fragmentation procedure is able to follow successfully the evolution of the GSD during tests reaching a vertical stress of 8 MPa.

Figure 6: Observed and computed volumetric strain in oedometer tests on pumice sands.

Figure 7: Evolution of grain size distribution in oedometer tests on pumice sand.
 a) Experimental observations b) Computations.

The virtual calibration chamber (Figure 8) has been constructed with the same procedure employed for silica uncrushed sand (Arroyo *et al.*, 2011) and a similar upscaling procedure for grains and cone has been used. The zero-strain radial lateral condition of the physical chamber was replicated by the model. Selected results of the DEM analyses are presented in Figure 9 where it is apparent that the cone penetration values are quite insensitive to the density of the sand, as observed in the physical experiments.

Figure 8: Virtual calibration chamber and cone.

Figure 9: Computed cone resistance of simulated cone penetration tests on pumice sand at different stress values. a) Loose specimen, b) Dense specimen.

Parallel DEM calculations assuming uncrushable grains were also performed, so that the effects of particle crushability could be readily identified. Results in terms of ratio of cone penetration resistance of uncrushable and crushable granular materials are collected in Figure 10. It can be noted that the pattern of variation with relative density agrees well with reported experimental results. No DEM results are available for densities below about 40% due to the difficulty of constructing very loose virtual specimens. In any case, it appears that the use of the new DEM

formulation for crushable materials provides a good tool to further explore penetration problems in this type of materials. More information on this study is given in Ciantia *et al.* (2016).

Figure 10: Effect of crushability on cone resistance for different relative densities. Experimental and DEM results.

3 CONTINUUM MODELLING

3.1 GENERAL

The continuum modelling of the cone penetration test has been performed using the Particle Finite Element Method, PFEM (Idelshon *et al.*, 2004; Onate *et al.*, 2004; Carbonell, 2009). The PFEM uses a Finite Element approximation to compute the movement of the particles within an updated Lagrangian framework. In this method particles and nodes coincide and the mesh is updated when required to prevent excessive distortions. Delaunay tessellation is used for this purpose. The mesh nodes are considered particles that carry mass and the state variables and, being particles, they can separate from the main domain, giving rise to new boundaries. For this reason, the Alpha Shape technique (Edelsbrunner & Mucke, 1994) is used to identify the boundaries at every step of the analysis. Further refinements involve the addition/removing of particles depending on a characteristic distance and the formulation of the contact conditions via a penalty method. Although the method was initially developed for fluid-solid interaction problems, there have already been some applications to geotechnical problems (Carbonell *et al.*, 2010; Zhang *et al.*, 2013, 2015).

Figure 11 shows a scheme of the method that can be summarised in the following steps:

- i) A cloud of particles, C_n , is defined at a time $t=t_n$,
- ii) identify the boundaries defining the analysis domain,
- iii) discretize the domain with a finite element mesh,
- iv) solve the governing equations within a Lagrangian formulation and compute the state variables at the next updated configuration at t_{n+1} ,
- v) move the nodes to the new position C_{n+1} ,
- vi) go back to step i).

Figure 11: Scheme of a PFEM computation step.

3.2 SINGLE PHASE FORMULATION

In a purely undrained case the soil can be considered as a single phase medium and only the linear momentum balance equation (equilibrium) needs to be solved. Accordingly, a total-stress Tresca constitutive model has been adopted to represent the soil whereas the tangential contact with the rigid cone has been simulated with a von Mises yield criterion. The analyses presented here have been performed with a rigidity index, $I_r = 100$. The geometry of the problem and the computation domain are shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Geometry and computational domain of the PFEM analysis of cone penetration.

The cone penetration analyses have been carried out using values of cone-soil adhesion ratio (α =adhesion/undrained shear strength) ranging from 0 to 0.7. The results in terms of cone penetration (normalized as cone factor N_{kt}) and

friction sleeve resistance are plotted in Figure 13. As expected, the friction sleeve resistance coincides with the specified adhesion and the cone resistance increases modestly with the value of adhesion. Figure 14 shows more explicitly the variation of cone factor with the value of adhesion.

Figure 13: Cone factor and friction sleeve resistance for different values of adhesion computed with PFEM.

Figure 14: Variation of cone factor with adhesion, α .

3.3 TWO-PHASE FORMULATION

The PFEM formulation has been extended to deal with coupled hydromechanical problems so that the full range of partially drained conditions and consolidation problems for saturated soils can be examined. Consequently, the formulation requires the simultaneous solution of the equilibrium equation and of the water mass conservation. Now, the soil constitutive models can be expressed in terms of effective stresses.

Using this formulation, the problem of cone penetration has been analysed adopting Modified Cam clay as the constitutive model for the soil. An explicit finite deformation integration of the constitutive law is used following the procedure outlined in Monforte *et al.* (2015). Figure 15 shows the contours of total displacements at three stages of penetration: initial and at normalised penetration ratios (z/R) of 6 and 10. z is the penetration depth and R the cone radius. $z/R=10$ corresponds to a steady state condition. The progress of the PFEM analysis is illustrated in Figure 16 where the evolution of the mesh during the calculation is presented. The refinement of the mesh of the soil domain directly affected by the penetration is apparent.

Figure 15: Total displacements during cone penetration. a) Initial, b) $z/R=6$, c) $z/R=10$. z : penetration depth and R : cone radius.

Figure 16: Evolution of the PFEM mesh during cone penetration. a) Initial, b) $z/R=6$, c) $z/R=10$. z : penetration depth and R : cone radius.

Figure 17 presents the variation of cone resistance with penetration depth showing that a steady state condition has been reached. Some oscillations in the solution can be noted; they result from the incompressibility of the soil at critical state combined with the use of low-order elements in the mesh. To address this issue, mixed formulations have been recently developed (Monforte *et al.*, 2016) that have proved very successful in overcoming this problem.

Figure 17: Variation of penetration resistance with depth. z : penetration depth and R : cone radius.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Two different approaches have been presented for the modelling of the cone penetration test that attempt to overcome the considerable difficulties associated with the simulation of penetration problems, i.e. large displacements, large strains and rotations, severe domain distortion as well as geometrical, material and contact nonlinearities. Both the DEM and PFEM procedures have shown their capabilities in this context although some significant challenges and shortcomings remain. They constitute, however, areas of intense development and research that should lead to an increasingly realistic description of the process of cone penetration in all its complexity. Consequently, it can be envisaged that more rational-based procedures for the interpretation of the test should ensue or, at least, a better understanding of the mechanisms underlying cone penetration should be achieved.

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